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Geometrical imperfection's effect on thermal buckling of cylindrical water storage tanks subjected to fire

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Abstract

Global warming and occurrence of different fires in forests and residential areas, motivate the use of fire extinguishing equipment, such as water storage tanks, which are becoming increasingly popular today. Maintaining the tanks due to high cost and their sensitivity to fire is very important. In this study, a 20 m diameter circular pool-fire adjacent to a reservoir is considered, and the resulting temperature distribution on the shell is deduced through the half-cosine temperature distribution relation. Nonlinear structural stability analysis is conducted by using the Riks nonlinear method in Abaqus/Standard environment. The effect of geometrical imperfection on the buckling behavior of the structure and the critical thermal load of the reservoir for different imperfection intensities are evaluated under variable parameters such as diameter to height ratio and fire scenarios. The results show that for the empty tank by increasing the diameter to height ratio, the sensitivity of the imperfection amplitude to the critical buckling temperature increases by up to 40%. In addition, it is indicated that the more local the thermal load, the less geometrical imperfection will affect the critical buckling temperature.

Keywords: Imperfection, Thermal Buckling, Pool-Fire, Storage Tank, Finite Element Method

Introduction

Protecting woodlands, suburban, and industrial areas from fire incidents and preventing the spread of fire to other regions has always been a human concern. Water storage tanks not only provide drinking water but also play a significant role in extinguishing a fire at the time of an accident. Due to their use and importance, these types of tanks must be constructed in such a way as to be resistant to high heat. Since their thickness to radius ratio is very small, they may buckle simply, if exposed to the heat load. Although most storage tanks do not catch fire directly, they may deform and stop operating because of absorbing heat from the surrounding flame. Hence, it is essential to study the behavior of these types of cylindrical shells subjected to thermal loading.

Buckling and post-buckling in cylindrical containers have long been recognized. Based on the experimental results obtained by Robertson [1], it was found that the buckling capacity of cylindrical shells was lower than the theoretical values. This incompatibility has led to much research in the following decades. All real structures have defects due to various reasons such as

geometry, loading conditions, uneven boundary conditions, residual stresses, and local thickness variations. Wilson and Newmark [2] showed that the difference between experimental and analytical values is due to several factors such as boundary conditions, undesired out of axis load, and, most importantly, the geometrical imperfection of the shell.

Due to the sensitivity of storage tanks, extensive research has been conducted in recent years to preserve storage tanks subjected to the heat load. The comprehensive researches of Liu [3] and Pantosa [4] are among the most noteworthy studies in this topic. In these articles, the buckling of the empty reservoir using two methods, Geometrically and Materially Nonlinear Analysis (GMNA) and Geometrically Nonlinear Analysis (GNA), were influenced by factors such as fluid level, pool-fire changes, geometrical imperfection, considering different roof thicknesses. Due to the high construction cost, recently the thermal buckling of storage tanks near fire has been studied considering individual parameters such as shell reinforcement, fuel type, different fire scenarios, and wind, as well as using various methods such as Computational Fluid Dynamic (CFD) fire modeling or the analytical buckling analysis methods such as Linear Bifurcation Analysis (LBA), GNA and GMNA [5-12].

In the present study, for the first time, the effect of geometrical imperfection intensity in thin-walled tanks under different fire scenarios such as increase and decrease in the heated area and the variation of tank diameter are studied. Further, these parameters' effects on the critical temperature and thermal buckling modes are investigated.

Methodology

Temperature Distribution due to Fire Loading

It is expected that the temperature distribution estimation due to fire loading will be the first step in the analysis of structural thermal stability. Because of the nonlinear essence of the fire phenomenon and its subtle interaction with structures, it is unpractical to use theoretical solutions in this realm. On the other hand, experimental work in this field is very costly and challenging. For this reason, a numerical approach is a feasible and cost-effective method to predict the behavior of structures under different pool-fire scenarios.

A pool-fire is considered to be a buoyant diffusion flame in which the fuel is positioned horizontally. If the pool-fire has a diameter equal to the target tank (Figure 1), Equation 1, known as the half-cosine temperature

distribution, can be used for obtaining the temperature distribution on the target periphery [3]:

$$T_{\theta} = \begin{cases} (T_{0m} - T_{0a}) \cos^2\left(\frac{\theta}{\theta_0}\right) & \text{if } |\theta| \leq \theta_0 \\ 0 & \text{if } |\theta| > \theta_0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Figure 1. Temperature distribution of the target tank [5]

In which T_{0m} and T_{0a} refer to the temperature of the most heated meridian and ambient temperature in °C, respectively. The circumferential coordinate and critical angle that clarifies the heated zone defined by θ_0 and θ , respectively. This non-uniform temperature distribution in the structure can lead to early buckling and, subsequently, destruction. Most storage tanks are made of stainless steel because of its cost-effectiveness and its ease of constructing such a massive cylinder. Therefore, it was assumed that the structure is made of steel 250. To improve the accuracy and predict the buckling behavior of the reservoir, changes in the material properties with increasing temperature must be appropriately incorporated into the problem. For this purpose, nonlinear variations in the mechanical properties, fracture, and thermal properties of the steel must be satisfactorily expressed. Besides, the geometrically nonlinear behavior of the structure must also be correctly considered in the analysis. Consequently, GMNA using the Riks method was implemented in Abaqus.

Structural Modeling

Structural modeling and discretization will be the next step in the proposed procedure in which the temperature distribution from the first step will be applied. Storage tanks often have a considerable height and diameter. The tank in this study has a height (H) and diameter (D) of 20 m, a shell thickness (t_c) of 1 cm, and a t_r/t_c ratio of 10, in which t_r defines roof thickness. The boundary conditions in these types of tanks are such that the bottom of the tank is fixed, and the roof is attached to the body, making a one-piece structure. Structural weight force influence the buckling behavior of the structure. Therefore, the gravitational force is taken into account. The temperature distribution displayed in equation 1 is used, and the tank's roof is supposed to be in cold temperature status.

The S4R shell element has been used for structural discretization. According to Figure 2, 67858 elements with approximately 0.3% error has been chosen as a trustworthy gridding mesh satisfying lower computational cost. The global mesh size was 0.5 meters, and 360 elements in the circumference of the circle have been modeled. Also, in regions of interest where more variation in stress and displacement were

anticipated, the number of elements has been increased by ten times.

Figure 2. Mesh independency results of the Riks method and the eigenvalues obtained for the target tank under Equation 1 conditions.

Geometrical Imperfections

Generally, none of the structures is perfect, and geometrical imperfections are one of the major sources of deviation from the perfect configuration. The main goal of the present research concerns the geometrical imperfection's effect on thermal stability.

To account for the geometrical imperfection in Abaqus, the buckling modes obtained by the eigenvalues method with different coefficients of thickness must be considered through coding in Python. To consider geometrical imperfection amplitude, it was assumed that the second and third modes has a coefficient of 10% and 1% of the first buckling mode, respectively and the first buckling modes were 0%, 10%, 20%, 40%, 60%, 80% and 100% of shell thickness.

Verification of Numerical Procedure

To examine the validity of the proposed numerical procedure, Liu's research [3] was used to compare the outcomes. The diameter, height, and thickness of the simulated reservoir were assumed to be 20, 20, and 0.01 m, respectively. Its roof had a 10 degrees slope and a thickness equal to three times the thickness of the cylindrical shell. The temperature distribution on the reservoir followed Equation 1. Figure 3 indicates the comparison between the Riks method simulation and the reference research data, which are in good agreement and have 2.1% errors on average. Note that δ_0 is imperfection amplitude, and t_c is shell thickness.

Figure 3. A comparison between simulation results and reference data

Results and Discussion

In order to better analyze the outcomes, the critical buckling temperature variations with imperfection amplitude in all parametric studies are expressed as dimensionless. In the diagrams of this section, the horizontal axis represents the dimensionless imperfection range obtained from the ratio of the first buckling mode to the shell thickness. On the other hand, the vertical axis indicates the critical dimensionless buckling temperature obtained by dividing the desired temperature (T_B) by 125 °C, which is the critical buckling temperature of an empty tank with 20 m diameter and height and is affected by ambient heat of 180 °C. The imperfection effect on two parameters, i.e., diameter to height ratios and heating zone, is discussed in the following sections.

Diameter to Height Ratio

Unlike the linear buckling analysis, the primary tool for analyzing nonlinear structural stability is the interpretation of Load Proportionality Factor (LPF) diagrams. Any sudden disruption in the monotonic trend of LPF curve could be interpreted as a fluctuation in the stability configuration of the structure. Figure 4 illustrates the LPF diagrams of storage tanks with two intensities of imperfection and illuminates the critical threshold of thermal loading. In comparison between perfect and imperfect tanks, severe displacement happens at a lower temperature in the latter one.

Figure 4. LPF diagram for perfect and 100% imperfect tank with D/H ratio of 1 and heating range of 180 degree

Figure 5 shows the buckling modes of the reservoirs for different diameters in perfect and 100% imperfect cases. As the diameter of the roof section increases, the effect of the roof weight has a substantial influence on the stability behavior of the structure. The cylindrical part of the reservoir in the presence of imperfections experiences harsh wrinkling patterns with high wave lengths, which are propagated along the structures' perimeter. The patterns in perfect structure have lower circumferential buckling wave lengths and amplitudes, and a relatively uniform axial lobe inflates the reservoir in the heat-affected zone. It is elicitable that the long circumferential buckling lobes in the imperfect reservoir could easily bring the structure to the margin of collapse and instability.

Figure 5. Buckling mode shapes with D / H ratio of: a) 1 for the perfect tank, b) 1.5 for the perfect tank, c) 2 for the perfect tank, d) 1 for 100% imperfect tank, e) 1.5 for 100% imperfect tank, F) 2 for 100% imperfect tank

The imperfection effect on the critical buckling temperature is illustrated by changing the D / H ratio in Figure 6. The graph shows that with increasing D / H ratios, the structural buckling decreases markedly, and additionally, with increasing geometrical imperfection, the critical buckling temperature for 1, 1.5 and 2 D / H ratios will decrease with a slope of about -15%, -24% and -31%. Accordingly, geometrical imperfection with increasing D / H ratio has more influence on the structural behavior and its critical buckling temperature.

Figure 6. Imperfection effects on critical buckling temperature for different diameter to height ratios

Heating Zone

In this part, the tank was subjected to different fire scenarios in the peripheral direction. In order to compare the effect of fire spread around the tank, the heating ranges of 135, 180, 225, and 270 degrees were considered. Figure 7 illustrates how the structure deforms at the time of buckling. A more uniform temperature distribution around the tank will produce more uniform thermal inflation. It is expectable that the vaster area of heat flux requires more energy to make the structure unstable. Therefore, the critical thermal buckling load will escalate when the heat zone expands.

The imperfection effect on the critical buckling temperature is analyzed by changing heating ranges demonstrated in Figure 8. the critical temperature of the perfect structure for the heating ranges of 180, 225, and 270 degrees will increase by 46%, 102%, and 171%,

respectively, compared to 135 degrees. Interestingly, in the narrower heat-affected zones, the less sensitivity trend to imperfection amplitude is observable. The mentioned sensitivity for 135, 180, 225, and 270 degrees of heat-affected zone will be -18%, -15%, -33%, and -30%, respectively. An increase in the area of the structure makes the tank more at risk from temperature variation because imperfection is probable to exist in all parts of the structure and affects its response.

Figure 7. Buckling mode shapes for heating range of a) 135 degrees for the perfect tank, b) 225 degrees for the perfect tank, c) 270 degrees for the perfect tank, d) 135 degrees for 100% imperfect tank, e) 225 degrees for 100% imperfect tank, f) 270 degrees for 100% imperfect tank

Figure 8. Imperfection effects on critical buckling temperature for different heating ranges

Conclusion

Initial geometrical imperfections are among the factors that influence the behavior of structures under different loading and boundary conditions. These defects, which usually occur during the manufacturing process, could be a factor in the buckling and failure of components and, in most cases, leads to the failure of the structure. Often the geometrical imperfection changes the buckling behavior of the thin-walled reservoirs from the local state to the global state and spread the damage around the structure.

As the ratio of diameter to height rises, the critical buckling temperature falls. By increasing the diameter

from 20 to 40 meters, the imperfection effect will have a more noticeable impact on the behavior of the structure.

The larger the heated area around the tank, the less destructive deformation is observed where the buckling is postponed, and the critical buckling temperature is increased due to the more uniform and global expansion behavior of the structure. According to the results, the geometrical imperfection has more influence on the structure with extensive heated area leading to more decline in critical buckling temperature. Moreover, the more local the heat and area of the deformation in the perfect case, the less the geometrical imperfection will affect the response.

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